

Effect of tillage practices on DWR grain yield, net income, and benefit:cost ratio.^a

Treatment ^b	Grain yield (t/ha)		Total cost (\$/ha)	Gross income (\$/ha)	Net income (\$/ha)	Benefit:cost ratio
	1988	1989				
Farmer's method, 4 plowings, with bullock-drawn country plow	2.8	3.1	158	338	180	2.1
1 moldboard plowing + 2 country plowings	3.4	4.0	149	423	214	2.8
1 moldboard plowing + 2 cultivations with bullock-drawn 3-tine cultivator	2.5	2.1	148	298	150	2.0
4 cultivations with tractor-drawn cultivator	2.3	2.2	161	259	98	1.6
2 cultivations with tractor-drawn cultivator + 2 country plowings	2.8	2.8	161	321	160	1.9
2 cultivations with tractor-drawn cultivator + 2 cultivations with bullock-drawn 3-tine cultivator	2.4	2.5	155	286	131	1.8
LSD (0.05)	0.1	0.3				

^aUS\$1 = Rs. 16.32. ^bPlanking after each plowing or cultivation.

1. Relationship between leaf blast severity (LB, scale of 0-7) and panicle blast incidence (PBI, percent) measured on IR50.

ship between LB and PBI was significant (Fig. 1). Regression analysis gave the following equations:

Simple linear:

$$PBI = 25.8825 + 11.2836 LB$$

$$r^2 = 0.94 \text{ (significant at } P = 0.0001)$$

Quadratic:

$$PBI = 16.216 + 20.95 LB - 1.381 LB^2$$

$$r^2 = 0.99 \text{ (significant at } P = 0.0001).$$

Plants without LB sustained some PB infection (average 14.15%), suggesting the possible involvement of external inoculum for PB infection. The data (not presented) also showed that variation in PBI was higher when LB was below 50% DLA. This may indicate that to assure uniform PB infection, LB severity earlier in the crop's growth would have to be at least 50% DLA.

Although a highly significant relationship between PBI at harvest and LB at maximum tillering is shown, our results do not provide any epidemiological explanation for the relationship. This points to the need for further experiments using whole plots.

The data gave a response surface (Fig. 2) described by the following equation for estimating yield loss (Y):

$$Y = 5.0725 + 0.3664 LB + 0.3301 PBI$$

$$r^2 = 0.72, \text{ (significant at } P = 0.01)$$

The equation suggests that, in the absence of PB, one point on the LB scale at maximum tillering causes approximately 0.4% yield loss; in the absence of

Integrated pest management—diseases

Using single hills to determine an equation for estimating yield loss caused by rice blast

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We used a modified single hill technique to estimate yield loss due to leaf blast (LB) and panicle blast (PB) caused by *Pyricularia grisea*, during 1988 wet season.

Different levels of blast severities were created by transplanting different densities of blast-infected seedlings and uninfected seedlings in a 2,500-m² irrigated lowland field.

At maximum tillering, when plants had the highest LB severity, 800 hills were randomly selected, tagged, and rated as 0 = no blast, 1 = 1-5 lesions/hill, 2 = 6-10 lesions/hill, 3 = 11-15 lesions/hill, 4 = about 10% diseased leaf area (DLA), 5 = about 25% DLA, 6 = about 50% DLA, and 7 = about 75% DLA.

The modified single hill technique requires that approximately 100 plants be tagged for each LB scale rating. In this experiment, only 509 hills out of the 800 tagged could be identified as having panicle blast incidence (PBI) and harvested to determine grain yield/hill. Because each rating on the LB scale represents a range of blast lesions, data from hills with the same LB ratings were grouped and average PBI percentage and yield for that rating calculated. Yield loss for diseased hills was calculated from the average yield of all hills with no LB or PB.

Relationships between LB and PBI, and between LB, PBI, and yield loss were estimated by regression analysis. To calculate the regression between yield loss and LB and PBI, loss was regressed against each group of hills with the same LB scale rating but different PBI, using the data from individual hills. Yield loss was used as the dependent variable.

LB severities ranged from 0 to 75% DLA, PBI from 0 to 100%. The relation-

LB, 1% PB incidence at harvest results in approximately 0.3% yield loss.

The magnitude of losses caused by PB is close to losses reported for other cultivars in field plot experiments in

Thailand and India. The modified single hill technique allows a preliminary estimate of yield loss in situations where it may be difficult to experiment with many blast severities. □

2. Response surface showing the relationship between yield loss (%), leaf blast (scale of 0-7), and panicle blast (% incidence, PBI) on IR50.

A new sheath rot (ShR) disease of rice identified in Tamil Nadu

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At the end of dry season 1990 (Apr-May), an unidentified ShR disease was observed on rice cultivars IR20 and TKM9 growing on experimental plots in Killikulam. Nearly 7% of rice plants at the boot leaf stage showed disease symptoms, mostly on the sheath enclosing the young panicle. Irregular, dark brown lesions covered much of the sheath. Panicles emerging from diseased plants were mostly black.

The pathogen was identified as *Curvularia lunata* (Walker) Boedijn (IMI

NO. 343370). To test pathogenicity on IR20, a single-grain 15-d-old culture was inserted between the flag leaf sheath and unemerged panicle at the boot leaf stage. The fungus produced characteristic ShR symptoms within 15 d. Symptoms on inoculated plants were similar to those on naturally infected plants.

Infectivity of the fungus was tested on other rice cultivars. A single-grain culture was inserted at the boot leaf stage. Test cultivars were transplanted at 2 seedlings/earthenware pot in insect-proof cages. Five replications of 10 seedlings each were used. Disease severity was scored 15 d after inoculation using a 0-9 scale: 0 = no disease, 1 = less than 1% sheath area affected, 3 = 1-5%, 5 = 6-25%, 7 = 26-50%, and 9 = 51-100% sheath area affected. ADT36, ADT38, IR50, ASD7, ASD8, and ASD17 were completely free of disease (see table).

Infectivity of *Curvularia lunata* on Tamil Nadu rice cultivars.

Cultivar	Damage score (0-9)
ADT36	0.0
ADT38	0.0
IR50	0.0
Co 37	5.6
MDU2	3.8
MDU3	5.7
ASD1	7.8
ASD2	9.0
ASD3	1.9
ASD4	2.8
ASD5	2.5
ASD6	4.8
ASD7	0.0
ASD8	0.0
ASD9	3.5
ASD10	5.4
ASD11	3.8
ASD12	7.5
ASD13	8.6
ASD14	3.0
ASD15	7.0
ASD16	5.5
ASD17	0.0
IR20 (check)	9.0
TKM6 (check)	9.0
LSD (P = 0.05)	0.7

The result was confirmed by a repeated experiment.

Several species of *Curvularia* are known to infect the rice grain, and may even cause leaf spots and seedling blight under certain conditions. But ShR due to *Curvularia lunata* had not been reported previously. □

Effect of asynchronized rice planting on vector abundance and tungro (RTD) infection

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Variation across fields in time of planting the rice crop lengthens the period for an increase in insect pests and diseases and shortens the fallow period during which the numbers of many pest species decline. Insect-transmitted diseases such as RTD are expected to be more prevalent in asynchronously planted areas, because their vectors are